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THE HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

D.R. Parmankulova N.D. Ergasheva

Khoja Akhmet Yassawi International Kazakh-Turkish University,
Turkestan, Kazakhstan

(Correspondin author's e-mail: dilafruz.parmankulova@ayu.edu.kz)

ABSTRACT

This article investigates the utilize of communicative strategies within the consider of a outside dialect, their role and points of interest within the improvement of lexicon within the common instructive prepare. Through the communicative methodology, the improvement of the communicative competence of understudies, their interface within the subject being examined are made strides. The communicative method is one of the strategies for rapidly and way better acing a certain point and makes a difference the understudy to memorize the magnificence of the dialect amid the learning and at the same time having fun handle. The creator pays extraordinary consideration to the presentation and utilize of dynamic vocabulary. Various sorts of communicative strategies given by the authour allow using the latest developments of cutting edge innovations. The idiosyncrasy of this learning prepare is that the work can be wiped out parts and after that combined. Permits you to pull in the greatest number of understudies, which makes for group building, intergroup communication.

Key words: audiovisual, visual, synthetic, linguists, methodology

ШЕТЕЛ ТІЛДЕРІН ОҚЫТУ ӘДІСТЕМЕСІНІҢ ДАМУ ТАРИХЫ

Д.Р.Парманкулова Н.Д.Эргашева

Қожа Ахмет Ясауи атындағы Халықаралық қазақ-түрік университеті
(Қазақстан, Түрікстан), e-mail: dilafruz.parmankulova@ayu.edu.kz

Бұл мақалада шет тілін оқытуға қатысты әдістерді қолдану, олардың жалпы оқу үдерісінде сөздік қорын дамытудағы рөлі мен артықшылықтары қарастырылады. Коммуникативті әдістеме арқылы оқушылардың коммуникативтік құзыреттілігін дамыту, оқытылатын пәнге деген қызығушылықтары жетілдіріледі. Коммуникативті әдіс белгілі бір тақырыпты тез және жақсы меңгеру әдістерінің бірі болып табылады және оқушыға оқу

барысында тілдің сұлулығын меңгеруге және сонымен бірге қызықты процеске көмектеседі. Автор белсенді лексиканы енгізуге және қолдануға ерекше көңіл бөледі. Автор ұсынған коммуникативті әдістердің әртүрлі түрлері заманауи технологиялардың соңғы әзірлемелерін пайдалануға мүмкіндік береді. Бұл оқу процесінің ерекшелігі жұмысты фрагменттерге бөліп, кейін біріктіруге болады. Студенттердің максималды санын тартуға мүмкіндік береді, бұл команда құруға, топаралық қарым-қатынас жасауға мүмкіндік береді.

Кілттік сөздер: аудиовизуалды, көрнекі, синтактикалық, лингвисттер, әдіснама.

ИСТОРИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ МЕТОДИКИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА

Д.Р. Парманкулова Н.Д. Эргашева

Международный казахско-турецкий университет имени Ходжи Ахмеда Ясави
(Казахстан, г. Туркестан), e-mail: dilafruz.parmankulova@ayu.edu.kz

В этой статье рассматривается использование коммуникативной методики в изучение иностранного языка, их роли и преимуществах в освоении лексики в общеобразовательных процессе. Посредством коммуникативной методики усовершенствуется развитие коммуникативной компетенции студентов, их интересы к изучаемому предмету. Коммуникативная методика является одним из методов быстрого и лучшего освоения определенной тематики и способствует обучающемуся познавать красоту языка во время обучающегося и одновременно развлекающегося процесса. Особое внимание автор уделяет внедрению и использованию активной лексики. Различные виды коммуникативной методики предоставленные автором позволяет использовать последние разработки современных технологий. Особенность данного процесса обучения заключается в том, что работа может быть выполнена фрагментами и после скомбинирована. Позволяет привлечь максимальное количество студентов, что создает для сплочения коллектива, межгруппового общения.

Ключевые слова: аудиовизуальные, визуальные, синтетические, лингвисты, методология.

In the literature on the history of foreign language teaching, the term "method" was used and is used generally in two ways: as the name of the method, the way of learning foreign languages proposed by any person or group (then write about

“a method of Comenius”, “Berlitz method”, etc.), and, as the title more or less significant set of learning principles that underlie a number of particular ways of learning (when talking about “direct”, “grammar-translation”, “communicative” methods). It is necessary to distinguish between these two meanings of the term “method”. In the latter case we can speak about the existence of certain schools in the methodology or, to use the wider concept, the presence of certain methodological directions.

So, if method is a way or method of teaching language, the General direction of the goal, under the methodological direction to be understood as the group of methods with common principles. The method of teaching foreign languages is a generalized implementation model of the main components of the educational process in a foreign language, which is based on a certain dominant idea of solving main teaching objectives[1]. If the training oral monologue speech regularly use the same form of the description of visually perceived scenes (paintings, drawings, filmstrips, etc.), in this case, generalized method of presentation of material will be by the method determined learning model. Method is evident when there is a systematic repetition of the same forms and methods of work for the successful solution of an iterative task of the learning process. The method covers a large number of common training situations in which it can function. Prominent educators give different definitions to the concept “teaching method”. Method is a way of joint activity of teachers and students in the learning process through which is achieved the task. I. L. BIM defines the method as “a method of activity, to the greatest extent for achieving the goal”.

“In the methodology of foreign language teaching historically ambivalent definition of a method as custom actions name concepts: a) method of training; b) method – a way of learning aspects of language and kinds of speech activity;” this implies that one methodological direction can include several methods of teaching foreign languages.

In the present work investigates the history of development of methodical directions in teaching foreign languages and methods as ways of learning aspects of language and kinds of speech activity are currently in teaching English. In order to analyze the modern methods of teaching foreign languages, we need to return to the history of language teaching and try to open the connection between teaching methods in the past and present[2]. This will give us the opportunity to use the experience of the past and help you deal in a variety of modern teaching methods, and therefore to select from this set the most effective methods of teaching English

Classification of methods of teaching foreign languages represents a complicated question as the basis of their names was based on a variety of characteristics. Depending on which aspect prevails in the teaching methods can be

lexical or grammatical. What logical categories are basic – synthetic or analytical. In accordance with the development of a skill is the purpose of training, there are the oral method and the reading method. The name of the method is determined by the admission, put in a basis of the language, such as audiovisual, visual. Also known methods are named by the name of their authors – methods of Berlitz, Guen, Palmer, Ussta, Frieze, Lado, Lozanova, Belyaev B. V etc.

For several centuries there were different methods or methodological directions in the teaching of foreign languages. All of these methodological directions are for a certain purpose and content of the training. But, on the other hand, methods of learning create the prerequisites to the contents of teaching foreign languages became wider. History of methods of teaching foreign languages knows numerous and diverse attempts to find the most efficient method of learning.

New methods of teaching foreign languages have emerged in response to the needs of society in language learning. With the advent of each new method often talked about creating efficient and versatile method of training. However, experience and research in the field of methods suggests that the creation of a generic method – the task is hardly feasible because the optimality of the method is determined by the specific goals, objectives, and learning environment [3]. As a starting indication of the method used, the approach to learning, which is characterized as a system of judgments about the nature of language and its learning. In modern methods received justification of different approaches to learning.

In their pedagogical heritage of the prominent place is occupied by thoughts on learning languages. Language is a means of communication and education. According to them in the language learning process should be based primarily on the text, vocabulary and grammar. Much time should be given practical exercises that are closely related to the rule. Vaysburd, M.L., put forward the principle of activity, consistency, availability, and consistency. It is recommended to go in learning from simple to complex, from concrete to abstract, from easy to hard. Opposed to learning words without sufficient understanding call the phenomena, has stressed the need for conscious language acquisition and compliance with the parallelism of things and words. He advised to use s an approach to linguistic facts and to consider the native language of the student, to use the principle of clarity as “the Golden rule of learning”.

The oldest method of teaching foreign languages is the natural method, which did not differ from the method by which the child learns the mother tongue. Foreign language mastered by imitating ready-made models, by repetition and play new material by analogy with the studied. The natural method of pursuing purely practical purpose – training first of all, the ability to speak and read light text long meet the needs of the society in which the productive command of a foreign language was the privilege

of its upper classes. With the emergence of schools and the introduction of the foreign language as a General subject for the first time also tried to teach the language in a natural method, but it was soon replaced by a transfer method.

b) the Linguistic system as an object of teaching foreign languages.

Conversion methods are rooted in the methodology of teaching the Latin language in XVI – XVII centuries. Methods of teaching living languages completely copied the methods of teaching the Latin language, although the concept of “foreign languages” arises quite independently of the Latin language.

At the turn of XVIII and XIX centuries there are “foreign languages” as a school subject from purely practical tasks. Since at the beginning the only goal of their study was reading books in those languages and because the teaching of the Latin language, the reading of the authors was prominent, so far as methods of teaching the Latin language was used in teaching foreign languages[4]. While the meaning of their study lay only in the ability to read the professional literature, the “grammar – translation” method was absolutely sufficient. Therefore, the traditional method of learning the Latin language in our time known as “grammatical-transferable.” This method is also called “synthetic”, i.e, going from elements to the whole, and as applied to the language – of words and forms – to phrases. Grammar - translation method focuses on teaching language as a system.

Until the late nineteenth century as the main object in teaching foreign languages were itself a language system. “The goal of language teaching is a message of knowledge about its General structure.” The language system is studied by means of transfer method, the four basic linguistic skills, not only speaking and listening but reading and writing. Therefore, great attention is paid to the analysis of the texts, writing summaries and essays. In addition, the student should learn the structure and logic of a foreign language, to be able to correlate it with relatives, to understand their similarities and differences. This is impossible without a serious study of grammar and practice without two-way translation. The basis of the grammatical - translation method is memorizing the rules of grammar, forms and vocabulary in order to be able to translate texts. Translation was the main purpose of this method. The center for the study of language form, but do not live it. Therefore, the textbooks are dated and meaningless exercises and assignments.

The contents transfer methods to determine such principles:

- consciousness, according to which the awareness of the students linguistic facts as they are learning, how they will be applied in speech communication. This principle is based on the leading role of thinking in the process of language acquisition and is opposed to the principle of intuitiveness characteristic of direct methods;

- parallel development of types of speech activity based on written language or on the basis of oral speech;
- organization of training in sequence – from the acquisition of knowledge and verbal skills;
- distribution of educational material for active and passive and its differential absorption resulting from the use of special exercises;
- comparison of similar and contrasting phenomena in the two languages with the aim of negative interference and using the results of positive transfer;

These methods are characterized by the separation of form and content. Thus, in the grammar-translation method, all the attention is directed to grammar, but the content side of the texts and the vocabulary is ignored.

Thus, in the practice of foreign language teaching language system was viewed as a global object of study until the first decades of the XX century.

c) Speech acts as the object of teaching foreign languages.

At the end of 19th century witnessed major economic changes in the countries of Western Europe. A number of economic, political and social factors determined the shift of focus from the language system in the speech act, the speech behaviour of a person in a foreign language.

The need for effective teaching foreign languages at a level suitable for communication, have raised serious concerns about adequate training methods. Grammar-translation method did not correspond to the purely practical purpose of learning living languages. "Until now, linguists were engaged almost exclusively written language, and even questions of phonetics interpreted in the aspect of the letters. In the second half of the XIX century linguists almost literally "discovered" living language with its unique pronunciation that do not fit into traditional letter formula. The concerted efforts of linguists, methodologists and teachers-practitioners have developed a new method of teaching foreign languages, which ideally sought to provide the students with the target language as a second «native language», and in this regard have focused on oral production. The direct method emerged at the base of the natural method Unlike the direct method from the natural was that it settled the then data of linguistics and psychology. No wonder among its founders were such prominent scientists-linguists, as P. Passy, N. Sweet, O. Jespersen, G. Wendt, etc. as a basic principle has been not a translation of, and adherence to oral language sample, imitation and memorization. The process of learning a foreign language has been kept "to learn by heart ready-made samples speaker's thoughts by imitation and constant repetition of their subsequent reproduction in various combinations".

From the standpoint of the representatives of the direct method, foreign language should be taught holistically and systemically, because, in their opinion, it is based on

the same psychological and physiological regularities when learning their mother tongue, and also acoustic and motor sensations play a crucial role.

The beginning of the XX century was marked by the adoption of a new object of study – verbal behavior, speech and actions that are consistent with the pragmatic goals of teaching foreign languages. Most clearly, speech practice, speech actions in a foreign language (as main subject of study) participated in the largest concept of the linguist, founder of structuralism in linguistics L. Bloomfield, according to which, between knowledge of language and possession there is no connection that the possession of language is a matter of practice.

Any skills learned through the same type of practice. To learn the language, you must practice and use it.

The methodical principles of teaching the direct method were as follows:

- the basis of learning is placed oral speech, as the language of nature sound and occupy a leading place sound and kinesthetic sensations, argued that psychology;
- with the exception of the native language and translation. This provision was based on studies that the words of the native language do not match with the words studied in terms of values, Express different concepts, etc., as each nation has its own worldview, a system of concepts, reflected in the language;
- special emphasis was placed on phonetics and pronunciation, as the mastery of the sound party of speech is a sine qua non verbal communication. This conclusion was based on the study of the sound side of language;
- the direct method recommended to study words in context, i.e. as part of the proposals;
- this method was suggested to study grammar-based induction. On the basis of well researched text, students conducted observations on the text and extract from it the rules;

Basic assumptions of this method and now are the basis on which to build learning foreign languages. This method was based on the same principle, where a child learns to speak their native language. The scheme is approximately as follows: a foreign word is illustrated by a picture, followed by the transition from single words to simple sentences with lots of question-answering exercises, further reading and writing[5]. Grammar is not explained, the rules of use of language memorized the standard offerings. The main objective is to achieve automaticity in speech activities. This method of learning sought to establish a direct connection without going through a mental translation into the native language, between word and object. Hence its name – the direct method. Classes of foreign languages by this method are extremely intensive, with constant activity as teacher and students. From the standpoint of the representatives of the direct method, foreign language should be taught holistically and

systemically, because, in their opinion, it is based on the psychological and physiological regularities when learning their mother tongue. The main role linguistic activities play memory and feeling, not thinking. During applications of the direct method provides for the establishment of direct connections between lexical units and grammatical structures of language and their values without reliance on the native language of the student[6].

A. N. Leontiev in the article “Some questions of psychology of learning speech in a foreign language”, speaking for the direct method of training. “I speak so because now we have a large number of well-established evidence that the speech in a foreign language and understanding, on the one hand, and translation on the other, are different processes with different structure. The actual process of speech is a process of transition from “speech plan” for his embodiment of the values of a language and further to realization in the external speech – oral or written. No matter how complex the process, it (also in cases of speech in a foreign language) not the scheme is: a speech-intention – value of native language – the meaning of foreign language – foreign speech. This is true for the process of understanding speech in a foreign language. [7].

The process of transition from verbal meanings of one language to the system of values in another language, the translation process, forms another and, moreover, are usually secondary functional system, has a different structure.”

L. V. Shcherba also played for training. “...the basic rule of proper methods of teaching foreign languages is that one should not even mentally translate from your native language...”.

The direct method, vocabulary acquisition takes place without the formation of strong relationships between the words of a foreign language and their native language. In such memorizing words included in the mechanical memory. This means that if words are not repeated, then over time, they inevitably fade from memory. But our memory works through a different mechanism, the mechanism of imprinting of the type "once and for all". Then the memory is formed like a "trap" for the word, and it finally triggers. This is the secret of getting rich quick dictionary in conditions when a person gets into the foreign language environment, and almost takes communication in a given language. That's why in the classroom is of great importance of live communication in a foreign language. But this speech must be real, must be real communication in the classroom.

For learning grammar in the direct method of teaching play a great role “speech model”. In this mastering grammar can happen that one or another grammar rule may apply to cases to which it does not apply. This phenomenon of speech in toddlers

described by Bloomfield L. ". The child says, for example, analogy with the known word foal or calf.

The practical results of this method — the students pretty quickly and well began to speak in a foreign language — brought him great fame.

Many experts agree that the direct method has made a positive contribution to the methodology of teaching foreign languages. Its positive elements include pronunciation teaching, memorizing ready-made phrases of living language, the implementation of the principle of clarity, the detailed design of different types of question-answering exercise. First of all, this method pays great attention to the phonetic side of the language. Further, based learning puts the learning of ready-made phrases (hence, the "reforms" you should basically admit analytic), mainly spoken language, comprehended preferably from the situation or in another visual way. In this regard, he pushes into the background the grammar, which, as in the native language, needs only to generalize and bring to consciousness are already known from practice. Finally, attempts to link the words of a foreign language with the concept not through the native language, and directly so, as in their native language [8]. In this regard, expels the native language of their lessons and forbids any transfers as a foreign language to native and back. This tends to insure learning a foreign language from its deforming influence of the native language".

At that time the greatest popularity was gained textbooks and courses M. Berlitz. The basic principles underlying the teaching of "M. Berlitz method" were as follows:

- the purpose of training is development of oral speech;
- perception of linguistic material must be carried out directly, i.e. immanent; the words of a foreign language should contact the subject or action, and the grammar should be intuitive, because such process is typical for mastering the child's native speech;
- learning material should be based on imitation and analogy; therefore, comparisons with the native language and surplus rules;
- disclosure of the meaning of words, grammar should be done with clarity (objects, actions, patterns);
- the main form of operation – dialogue.
- the whole material of the language previously perceived by the ear (the mastery of the pronunciation), and then worked through orally (by different authors differently in terms of duration) and using a significant amount of time reading, starting with the individual words;

In relation to these principles was built and all the training. So, in the textbook M. the Berlitz first pages of the book were filled with drawings with captions depicting the individual objects mainly school auditorium. Such oral start, which concerned the

introduction of new material in subsequent paragraphs, the author justified the fact that the student must first hear the original pronunciation and the model that you should emulate.

The aim of the research work to investigate prospective English language learners communicative competence in the study of a foreign language, and English learning teaching environment their role and advantages in the development of vocabulary in the general educational process. Therefore for this purpose the present study took up with the following research will be discussed in detail in result section.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Curious was built on learning to read. Originally read previously learned words without their exploding, and only a few lessons explained the reading of the individual letters, phrases. In other words, practicing reading words issues.

The second direct method is watching the children found out that learning mother tongue, children accompany their actions with toys comments in chronological order type: Bear goes to sleep. Bear falls asleep. Bear sleeps, etc. Therefore the main place in the system of F. Guen takes the position that it is natural to teach language to the actions of the man, his experiences in chronological order. It followed the position of his system and training unit, around which the training is to offer, and connecting grammar and vocabulary. The progress of his method was the following:

- first, the teacher performs the actions and at the same time says;
- students then follow the teacher repeat each sentence;
- then the teacher says some phrases, and students perform the action;
- strong student then pronounces the sentence, and others perform actions;
- completed work oral naming of actions (all pupils) and their implementation;

After such training based on mechanical imitation of the students possessed limited material mostly spoken language. A major representative of the direct method was . Bondi E.A. connected learning a foreign language with an active activity of students, attaching great importance to the emotional side of perception of the world. In accordance with this he tried to bring the training to familiarize learners with the target language country. M. Walter for the first time systematized the practice groups as a tool for memorizing vocabulary. So, he proposed to group words according to the principle of synonyms and antonyms, thematically, the same root word. The basis for the memorization of words was the establishment of associations, as proposed associative psychology, insisting on the fact that the strength of memory increases by relying on the association.

First of all, it should be noted that representatives of the direct method proposed system of semantization of vocabulary: demonstration of the object, its image, demonstration actions using facial expressions; disclosure of the meaning of words

through synonyms, antonyms or definitions; disclosure of the value using context[9]. All these methods of semantization experienced many methodological directions and entered the modern methods of teaching foreign languages. Found a place in modern technique and commenting on the action, especially at the initial stage, as well as the use of drama. All this suggests that the legacy of this direct method is not lost

The great contribution of the direct method in foreign language teaching methods cannot be doubted, and learning oral foreign language cannot go past the gains of the direct method. First of all, the pronunciation teaching of today can be put to good reasons. Further, a fully developed system of speech material to be mastered at early stages of learning, and the method of its submission. Especially much effort has been devoted to the development of the principle of clarity in teaching foreign languages, which was very valuable for students of younger ages. "Certainly, a merit of representatives of the direct method was to develop an inductive approach to teaching grammar. First, it was shown that words of different languages reflect the different Outlook of the people, although was not quite the right conclusion about using it means of semantization. Pay attention to the requirements to the texts developed by N. The EN-Suite. Finally, we systematized means of semantization of vocabulary". [10].

The direct method in its purest form did not last long, but its significance for the development of the technique, as we have said, it was great. Many of its provisions in its pure form or transformed, reformulated and are used in modern methods.

The direct method was further developed by G. Palmer and M. West. But they moved away from prysma in its extreme expression. The influence of these two methodists noticeable in varying degrees in virtually all methodological directions.

Representatives of prysma are H Frieze and Methodist R. Lado, who has published several theoretical works and textbooks for learning foreign languages. As for the ultimate goal of learning H Frieze and R. Lado put forward a comprehensive foreign language, i.e. all types of speech activity. Considering language as a reflection of history, culture and life of the people carrier of this language, R. Lado believes that learning a foreign language is inextricably linked to the penetration into the culture of its people, as they are inseparable and cannot be understood one without the other. It is impossible to understand other people (and his language), if you do not master the system of concepts, which in turn, is possible only in the language of the people, as the speakers of another language operate on different concepts. An insight into the culture of the people, the knowledge of his system of concepts are not only educational, but also practical value. A serious attention in theoretical studies they have to the distinction between passive and active language material. Recognizing the object of study proposal, which they consider the unit of oral communication, A. Frieze and R. Lado build accordingly and all language training, nor in isolation without considering

the individual words or grammatical forms. In their opinion, the basis of language teaching is sound material and structure. They do not attach importance to vocabulary of the language, which should only serve as an illustration of the reported structures. From the vocabulary they choose first drill of the word, and then fittingly, since knowledge of combatant words gives you the ability to build sentences and understand them by ear. Thus, the leading is the mechanical mastery of the grammar of the language on the material of the endless number of related proposals which provide the basis to relate their method to the grammatical type. Among the appeared in the early 60-ies of XX century methods of teaching foreign languages special attention attracted the audiovisual method, based on an integrated use of technical means, providing a visual-aural synthesis in the teaching of foreign languages, which significantly considered the learning process. The method, which is based on the use of structures, has as its goal to bring students to ensure that they quickly made offers, without resorting to the mediation of the native language and the rules of normative grammar.

What are the principles of the audiovisual method?

- Material for teaching should serve as a spoken language in dialogue form. The authors of the method come from the position that it is a continuous dialogue between people. Moreover, this dialogue occurs. Therefore, educational process should be organized so as to create a situation in which use of the most common lexical items and grammatical structures[11]. Classes in AVM are conducted in an atmosphere of natural speech. It stimulates the absorption of correct intonation and, of course, and meets the practical learning objectives.

- Native language should be excluded from the learning process. Semantization is due to the image, where each phrase corresponds to a visual image.

- Perception of structures should occur only on the ears, and the emphasis is on unity sound image: sounds, intonation, rhythm should form a coherent whole.

- All structures of the language are perceived globally. Therefore, the entire material (both lexical and grammatical and phonetic) are introduced into the framework structures. R. Michea, one of the theoreticians of the AVM believes that the structures varying from language to language, are the most stable phenomenon of the native language and the most difficult moment in learning a foreign language. Task for student: to listen, to imitate, and then to use these structures. The main principle of training for AVM is that it is purely verbal. Only after 70 hours of oral classes students begin writing. Interestingly, the transition is carried out to the letter, and then to reading. First written dictation of words with phonetic spelling.

Key words and expressions, spelling of which should be remembered by the students as a whole, allocated in the framework and are written by the teacher on the

chalkboard. After the phonetic grammar dictations are given, which aim at the learning of spelling of verbs.

Thus, the first vocabulary, then grammar, then phonetics. But it is not allocated separately, and is in the phrases. This method, can be successfully used to teach tourists (massive training), but for school it is unlikely to be acceptable.

CONCLUSION

Analyzing the results of the work, based on the data laid down in the goal, the following conclusions were made:

Direct method or its modifications not solve all the problems related to the teaching of foreign languages. The fact is that when teaching the direct method assumes that with increasing tenure a living language grows and the intuitive ability to grasp the meaning of texts both in their native language. However, in practice it turned out:

- Give the school the same knowledge of a living foreign language, what we have in the native language, it is almost impossible (the amount of material that we have to hear the lessons of a foreign language, can not be even compared to our experience in native language).

- Another disadvantage of direct method is that the center of gravity when it is rote memorization of samples and the unconscious imitation of them, and it brings educational value of lessons in foreign languages by the direct method almost to zero.

- Although the desire direct method to do knowledge of a foreign language is completely independent of the native, and thus protect it from the influence of the latter is legitimate and methodically essentially correct, however in practice it suffers a complete collapse: the surrounding us, life is stronger than all those artifices, which prescribes the direct method. Native language still exerts its distorting influence on foreign language learners. Meanwhile, the measures taken by the direct method to eliminate the influence of the native language, are very disadvantageous for the process of learning a foreign language. The requirement to do without the students ' native language when thinking about certain words of a foreign language is often a large expenditure of time, energy, and ingenuity, which in most cases turns out to be non-productive as a full understanding usually comes only when students find a corresponding equivalent in the native language. In addition, this requirement makes it absolutely impossible to explain to the students about more subtle linguistic phenomena that leads to the devaluation of foreign language learning from an educational point of view. There is no need to prove how important the use of the native language in the first stage of training as a means of semantization.

After all, no equivalent was found among the words of the native language the understanding of new foreign words is a fuzzy and approximate. Even if the illustrative method of operating the native language remains means of understanding. Showing an

object and naming it in a foreign language, the teacher expects that the subject of the audience is familiar. But the subject might be familiar only through knowledge of the native language.

- Proved untenable and the concept of direct method of learning a foreign language in the same way as native. The native language of the growth is the first person of the only means of communication and instrument of thought, and foreign is neither the one nor the other. When learning a foreign language, especially in the first stage, the native language remains the primary means of understanding and expressing thoughts. If the native language is absorbed in vivo, a foreign language is artificial.

Our research suggests, in fact, how to teach adults by the direct method is very difficult. Persons accustomed to independent thinking, to mental work, quickly tired of the naivety, simplicity of questions and answers. At the same time, interesting texts for a long time remain unavailable. Interest in language is lost, the more those adults often do not have enough time for hard work, or simply aging. It is not surprising that, despite a disappointment in the direct method, and began the search for a compromise between the old, grammar-transfer method and the new, who had already become outdated, – the direct method. Modifications of different methods.

In contrast to the number of revealed shortcomings of the direct method of teaching foreign languages, scientists began to pay attention to the conceptual and semantic side of the phenomena, especially the processes related to the mental activities of the students for solving their problem and unusual problems. In the struggle between the grammatical-transferable and reformed methods had different modifications and a gradual qualitative perfection of the two primary methodological areas.

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Information about authors:

1. Parmankulova D.R. ([contact person](mailto:dilafroz.parmankulova@ayu.edu.kz)) – Master of Philological Sciences of Khoja Akhmet Yasawi International Kazakh-Turkish University, Turkestan, Kazakhstan; e-mail: dilafroz.parmankulova@ayu.edu.kz
2. Ergasheva N.D- Master of Philological Sciences of Khoja Akhmet Yasawi International Kazakh-Turkish University, Turkestan, Kazakhstan